

Exploring Machine Learning for Cloud Segmentation in Thermal Satellite Images of the FOREST-2 Mission

Niklas Wölki^{1,2}, Lukas Kondmann¹, Christian Mollière¹, Martin Langer¹, Martin Werner², Julia Gottfriedsen¹

¹*OroraTech GmbH, Munich, Germany*

²*Technical University of Munich (TUM), Munich, Germany*

Thermal remote sensing is critical for climate monitoring but is often hindered by clouds. Accurate cloud detection is essential for users of this data, however, research on cloud detection within the thermal domain is limited so far. In this paper, we explore cloud detection with long-wave infrared images of the FOREST-2 mission. We create a global, manually labeled dataset of 528 images. A UNet with a MobileNet encoder balances model size and performance well with a macro F1 score of 0.819 and an accuracy of 0.873. Also, Gradient Boosting performs best among more traditional techniques with 0.762 macro F1 and 0.877 accuracy. This provides a starting point for thermal-only research to inform upcoming constellations.

1 Introduction

Thermal remote sensing informs a variety of impactful applications in earth monitoring, such as fire detection [1], agricultural monitoring [2, 3], urban heat [4], and industrial monitoring [5]. However, there is currently a gap in high-resolution thermal data with a frequent revisit rate. Landsat offers 100m thermal resolution but has a revisit rate of 16 days only [6]. On the other hand, MODIS has near daily revisits but a km-level resolution. Public missions like LSTM and Thrishna may help but they will only launch towards the end of the decade. Thermal cubesats, such as the upcoming FOREST constellation, can close this gap. With already two satellites in orbit and eight more to launch until the start of 2025, the FOREST constellation will achieve a global revisit time of twice a day starting 2025.

Clouds, however, often obstruct thermal observations. Beyond that, clouds in thermal images are not as easy to spot for algorithms as with optical images. Thin clouds may at times not be visible at all and even thick clouds may have similar temperatures to mountain peaks. Sometimes, visible channels are available to help but this requires a lot of power, downlink and physical space on a shoebox-sized satellite. Because

of this, there is a necessity for accurate and reliable cloud masks using only thermal images.

Some existing work has explored cloud detection in thermal imagery but primarily from the ground up [7, 8]. On the other hand, ample work exists on cloud detection with multispectral images or in combination with other domains [9, 10]. However, little is known about cloud detection for upcoming thermal cubesat constellations, particularly when only thermal data is available.

In this paper, we adapt and benchmark classical machine learning and deep learning techniques for thermal cloud detection with FOREST-2 imagery. For this purpose, we curate a hand-labeled dataset of 24 large FOREST-2 scenes across the globe which we process into about 500 256 x 256 crops. We find a UNet segmentation architecture with MobileNet v3 large as encoder to be the most promising model on our FOREST-2 dataset as it balances performance and computational efficiency well. It reaches a macro-averaged F1 score of 0.819 and accuracy of 0.873 across a 6-fold cross-validation. Among classical machine learning methods, Gradient Boosting works best with an overall macro F1 score of 0.762 and accuracy of 0.877. Overall, the majority of UNet style encoders based on deep learning models surpass classical machine learning techniques but require longer training and inference speed.

2 Data

FOREST-2 is a thermal cubesat mission launched in summer 2023 with three thermal bands (MWIR, LWIR1, LWIR2). We primarily use the two LWIR bands for the cloud detection task as the FOREST-2 MWIR band is tweaked for fire detection and not really usable for cloud segmentation. We collect a hand-labeled dataset of 24 FOREST-2 scenes from various regions. The summary statistics of our dataset are pre-

	Cloudy	Clear	Total
Day	12.5%	21.8%	34.3%
Night	14.4%	51.3%	65.7%
Total	26.9 %	73.1%	100%

Table 1: Distribution of pixels in the dataset for LWIR1 band. About two in three scenes are taken at night and 27 % of pixels are cloudy.

sented in Table 1 for the LWIR1 band. We labeled the LWIR bands separately but report by default LWIR1 in this paper because results look similar. Overall, 26.9% of pixels are cloudy and 73.1% are clear creating an imbalance between the two segmentation classes. Of the included scenes, about a third were taken during the day and two thirds at night. Early observations of FOREST-2 were taken across the globe in principle but are more frequent over wildfire-prone regions such as Australia and North America. All continents apart from South America are represented in the dataset, however. Nevertheless, we acknowledge spatial limitations and potential generalization issues in our comparably small dataset.

We separate the images into up to 30 crops per scene with 256 x 256 pixels. Crops are allowed to overlap up to 25%, resembling some popular data augmentation techniques. Overall, this results in 528 images. One potential issue that could arise from the overlapping crops is label leakage between training, validation and test folds. To prevent this and make the most of the comparably small dataset we opt for a spatial cross-validation strategy for training and evaluation [11]. Scenes that are geographically close to each other end up in the same fold which prevents leakage and incentivizes spatial generalization. Overall, we split the 24 scenes into 6 folds with crops from 4 scenes each for training and validation of evaluated methods. We iteratively use four folds for training a respective method, one for validation during the training and hold out one fold to obtain a final test score. These test scores are then averaged across the six folds.

3 Methods

We test three kinds of models: Thresholding, Traditional Machine Learning and Deep Learning.

Thresholding: As a baseline, we employ a binary thresholding approach for the cloud segmentation task. We determine two thresholds based on the training data t_1 and t_2 . Any pixel with a brightness temperature below t_1 was a cloud in the training data because clouds are typically colder than most of the surface. On the other hand, any pixel above t_2 was

clear. Between t_1 and t_2 we linearly interpolate cloud probabilities proportionally to the distance to t_1 and t_2 combined with Otsu thresholding. This approach does not involve learning but uses a simple temperature heuristic to classify clouds.

Traditional Machine Learning methods: Given the comparably small size of our dataset, traditional machine learning methods such as Random Forests [12] or Gradient Boosting [13] may offer a good balance between performance and computational efficiency. Both are decision tree-based methods. Random Forests operate by fitting many shallow trees, utilizing random samples from available variables and observations, thereby reducing overfitting and improving generalization. In contrast, Gradient Boosting takes an iterative approach, fitting trees sequentially to the residual errors of prior trees. This allows it to refine predictions iteratively and effectively capture complex patterns in the data.

Deep Learning Methods: UNet [14] is a seminal segmentation architecture that has been pioneered in medical image segmentation and applied with success across many domains. Following this success, the encoder-decoder architecture of its segmentation approach has been combined with established and pretrained encoder architectures. Beyond a standard UNet, we therefore also test a collection of large convolutional models as encoders in a UNet segmentation architecture. ResNets[15] established skip connections to circumvent previous limitations of very deep architectures. MobileNets[16] strike a balance between the success of convolutional models and model size with up to three million parameters only. Efficiency and inference speed are relevant input since computational resources, particularly on orbit, may be limited. In similar spirit, we also include EfficientNet [17]. EfficientNet uses neural architecture search to drive down the number of parameters while maintaining stable image recognition performance. This model selection reflects the trade-off between model accuracy and potential inference on-orbit with limited compute and power available.

Model Training: The classical UNet model is trained from scratch as a comparison point for pretrained backbones. All other deep learning models are initialized with their ImageNet pretrained weights. As our models handle single channels instead of three channel RGB imagery, we add an additional trainable convolutional layer in front of the model to bridge this difference. We train for 200 epochs with balanced Binary Cross Entropy loss, ADAM as optimizer and a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} . We choose the model with the lowest validation loss after those 200 epochs.

Evaluation Criteria: We rely on macro-averaged F1 score and accuracy as main criteria. Accuracy is the

percentage of correct classifications. In terms of True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP) and False Negatives (FN):

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN} \quad (1)$$

The F1 score balances recall and precision and is defined as follows:

$$F_1 = \frac{2 * \text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

We opt for a macro-based aggregation which means that we derive the F1 score per class and then average the classes with equal weights and not according to their frequency. This further incentivizes balanced decision making in contrast to accuracy which has limitations with class imbalance.

4 Results

Model	Macro F1	Accuracy
Thresholding	0.693	0.752
Random Forest	0.726	0.835
Gradient Boosting	0.762	0.877

Table 2: Benchmark scores of thresholding and traditional ML methods on our dataset for LWIR1. Scores are the average of a 6-fold cross-validation. Gradient Boosting outperforms thresholding and Random Forests on our dataset with a margin of about 5 percentage points (p.p.) in macro F1 and 6 p.p. in accuracy.

Table 2 presents the macro F1 score and accuracy averaged across the test folds after training and evaluation with six-fold cross-validation for thresholding, Random Forest, and Gradient Boosting. The naive thresholding approach classifies about three out of four pixels correctly, with an accuracy of 0.752 and a macro F1 score of 0.693. The classical machine learning methods exceed this performance here. Random Forest achieves a Macro F1 score of 0.726 and an accuracy of 0.835. The best scores in Table 2 is from Gradient Boosting with a macro F1 of 0.762 and an accuracy of 0.877. This implies that roughly eight out of nine pixels are classified correctly at test time which is significantly better than with thresholding and Random Forests. It seems that Gradient Boosting performance is comparably strong compared to other tree based methods or our heuristic baseline on our dataset.

Figure 1: Different pretrained encoders as a backbone in UNet style cloud segmentation architectures. Their macro-averaged F1 score (x-axis) is plotted together with the number of parameters (y-axis). ResNet 152 stands out as the best model overall. However, the MobileNet large achieves almost the same performance with about 5% of the model size only.

As Gradient Boosting comes with high computational efficiency but a limited number of parameters, there may be more potential for deep learning based methods to explore. This potential, however, may come with an increase in computational cost. Figure 1 plots the deep learning results with their macro F1 score on the x-axis and the number of parameters of the model on the y-axis. The best models would therefore be in the bottom-right corner as similar performance with a lower number of parameters is preferable. The classical UNet architecture trained from scratch reaches a macro F1 score of about 0.75 which falls behind Gradient Boosting here. All other models - initialized with pretrained imagenet weights - surpass the performance of Gradient Boosting at 0.762. A large version of EfficientNet (b7) achieves a macro F1 score above 0.8. On average even better are ResNets and MobileNets of different sizes which all score above 0.8 macro F1. The best model in terms of F1 is ResNet152 with an F1 score of 0.820. However, MobileNet v3 large captures almost the same score with 0.819 but with about 5% of the parameters only. Both MobileNets, small and large, perform comparably strong given their small size. The respective accuracy of the MobileNet large is at 0.873 which is in the range but just below the boosting model. So the MobileNet does not classify more pixels correctly overall but its performance is more homogeneous across the two classes.

The overall goal of these experiments is a pipeline for cloud detection for full Forest-2 scenes. Figure 2 displays such a scene where small clouds in high num-

bers obscure ground views. The full scene has a slight inclination from the overpass of the satellite. An example of the possibilities with the MobileNet large encoder within a UNet architecture is in Figure 3. We can now flag pixels with a high likelihood to be affected by clouds in their temperatures. Overall, the exemplary cloud mask seems to identify the regions of cloud cover well but slightly overestimates the shapes. One could argue, however, that this property (at least to an extent) is desirable because nearby pixels may still be affected even if it is not directly visible in the image. In summary of our results, we have tested a variety of different methods for cloud detection on FOREST-2 images with thermal inputs only. UNet based pretrained encoders for segmentation worked best where particularly MobileNets stood out with high performance and low parameter numbers. The performance of Boosting lacked balance but reached similar accuracy. Therefore, Gradient Boosting may be a viable alternative if computational resources are too low to take on even small deep learning models. This may be particularly relevant for on-orbit processing with cubesats where hardware is fairly limited.

Figure 2: Forest-2 LWIR Image with clouds visible (dark)

Figure 3: Predicted clouds with the MobileNet model.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The dataset is relatively small, and the scene locations are not random as they are related to factors like fire proneness. This may result in an unrepresentative

dataset. Still, our scores provide a first indication of the suitability of each of these methods for the task at hand. Nevertheless, one could hypothesize, for example, that larger models such as ResNet152 would have more of an edge if more labeled data was available. One option for future work is to use existing label corpi for cloud detection with available thermal bands such as from Landsat. These could either serve as additional validation source or be combined into the FOREST-2 training as related labels in a transfer learning domain. Additional labels could also help with the class imbalance of cloud detection, for example through oversampling. Beyond more labels, there are several methodological avenues that are still open to be explored while thermal-only cloud detection is still in its infancy. This includes but is not limited to transformer-based segmentation models [18, 19] or self-supervised pretraining [20]. Finally, the vision for many of the thermal cloud detection algorithms would be to run on-orbit which comes with a whole set of constraints in terms of power, available software, model size and runtimes. In ongoing work, we are investigating opportunities to transfer our results to on-orbit cloud detection for operational and future satellites.

To conclude, we have explored several promising approaches for on ground cloud detection in thermal images. This matters because visible imagers are not always available or usable on thermal satellites. For this purpose, we manually labeled a small dataset of 24 FOREST-2 scenes, resulting in 528 images of 256 x 256 size. Our results show that thermal-only cloud detection seems possible even with comparably small algorithms. Gradient Boosting reaches an accuracy of 0.877 with a macro-averaged F1 of 0.762 which seems competitive given its small size. Going larger in terms of model size with deep learning, increases macro F1 performance up to 0.82 at similar accuracies. MobileNet v3 large seems to balance model size and performance for thermal cloud detection the best but larger models may be more suitable once more labeled data is available. Still, small and accurate models open the door for on-orbit thermal cloud detection which is an exciting field for upcoming cubesat missions.

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